

Extemporized new sets in grill topological spaces

G. Selvi¹ and I. Rajasekaran^{2*}

¹Department of Mathematics, Saveetha School of Engineering, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Science, Chennai - 602 105, Tamil Nadu, India. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-4980-163X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4980-163X)

²Department of Mathematics, Tirunelveli Dakshina Mara Nadar Sangam College, T. Kallikulam-627 113, Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu, India. ORCID iD: [0000-0001-8528-4396](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8528-4396)

Received: 08 Jul 2023

Accepted: 30 Jul 2023

Published Online: 31 Aug 2023

Abstract: This aim of this research is to study the modern sort of open sets and introduces and examines a new class of $t^\#$ -sets defined in terms of a Grill on X . Such sets' characterization and a few more characteristics are discovered.

Key words: $\mathcal{G}_t$ -open sets, $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}}$ -open sets, $\mathcal{G}_{t_\alpha}$ -open sets and $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}_\alpha}$ -open sets.

1. Introduction

The study of generalised types of closed sets has recently piqued the interest of many Topologists. Levine [4], for instance, pioneered a certain type of generalised closed sets. The definition of a type of generalised closed sets, which has been developed and studied, is in line with the trend.

Choquet [2] was the first to present the idea of a Grill. W.J. Thron has introduced [14] Proximity structure and grills. After him Roy and Mukherjee [11] published an article in on a common topology brought about by a grill topological spaces. In 2010 Hatir and Jafari [3] introduced on a few new sets classes and a fresh grill-based decomposition of continuity and finally M.O.Mustafa and Esmael [6] are discussed in their article about topological open grill separation axioms and closed sets in 2021.

Following investigations have shown that grills can be a very helpful tool for looking into a variety of topological issues.

The objective of this paper is to introduce and investigate a sophisticated class of $t^\#$ -sets and $t_\alpha^\#$ -sets defined in respect of a Grill on X . A description of previous sets is obtained along with some of their characteristics.

2. Preliminaries

The closure set and the inner set of D for a topological space (TS) (X, τ) , $D \subseteq X$, and Grill Topological Space (GLTS) are referred to as $C(D)$ and $I(D)$ respectively throughout this work.

Theorem 2.1. [11]

It can be admitted that $(X, \tau, \mathcal{G})$ is a Grill Topological Space (GLTS). For $D, E \subseteq X$, the ensuing properties hold:

1. $D \subseteq E$ indicates that $\Phi(D) \subseteq \Phi(E)$.

2. $\Phi(D \cup E) = \Phi(D) \cup \Phi(E)$.
3. $\Phi(\Phi(D)) \subseteq \Phi(D) = C(\Phi(D)) \subseteq C(D)$.
4. If $U \in \tau$ then $U \cap \Phi(D) \subseteq \Phi(U \cap D)$.

Theorem 2.2. [11] If D and E are the subsets of X in a space $(X, \tau, \mathcal{G})$, the beneath said answers are correct for the set operator ψ .

1. $D \subseteq \psi(D)$,
2. $\psi(\phi) = \phi$ and $\psi(X) = X$,
3. If $D \subseteq E$, then $\psi(D) \subseteq \psi(E)$,
4. $\psi(D) \cup \psi(E) = \psi(D \cup E)$.
5. $\psi(\psi(D)) = \psi(D)$.

Definition 2.1. A subset D of space $(X, \tau, \mathcal{G})$ as

1. grill α -open (resp. $\mathcal{G}_\alpha$ -open) [1] if $D \subseteq I(\psi(I(D)))$,
2. grill pre-open (resp. $\mathcal{G}_p$ -open) [3] if $D \subseteq I(\psi(D))$.
3. grill semi-open (resp. $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open) [1] if $D \subseteq \psi(I(D))$.
4. grill b -open (resp. $\mathcal{G}_b$ -open) [1] if $D \subseteq I(\psi(D)) \cup \psi(I(D))$.
5. grill β -open (resp. $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open) [1] if $D \subseteq C(I(\psi(D)))$.

Definition 2.2. [8] A subset D of GLTS $(X, \tau, \mathcal{G})$ is discovered to be

1. grill t -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set) if $I(D) \subseteq I(\psi(D))$,
2. grill $\mathcal{R}$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_\mathcal{R}$ -set) if $D = D_1 \cap D_2$, where D_1 is open and D_2 is $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set.

3. On new sets in grill topological space

Definition 3.1. A subset H of a GLTS $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$ is revealed to be

1. grill $t^\#$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_{t^\#}$ -set) if $I(V) = \psi(I(V))$.
2. grill $t^\#_\alpha$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_{t^\#_\alpha}$ -set) if $I(V) = \psi(I(\psi(V)))$.
3. grill $\mathcal{R}^\#$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}^\#}$ -set) if $V = R \cap S$, where R is open & S is $\mathcal{G}_{t^\#}$ -set.
4. grill $\mathcal{R}^\#_\alpha$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}^\#_\alpha}$ -set) if $V = R \cap S$, where R is open & S is $\mathcal{G}_{t^\#_\alpha}$ -set.
5. strong grill $\mathcal{R}$ -set (resp. $\mathcal{G}_{S\mathcal{R}}$ -set) if $V = R \cap S$, where S is $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set and R is open, $I(\psi(S)) = \psi(I(S))$.

Remark 3.1. For a GLTS $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$,

1. if L is open $\implies L$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}^\#}$ -set.
2. if L is $\mathcal{G}_{t^\#}$ -set $\implies L$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}^\#}$ -set.

Remark 3.2. In every part of the Remark 3.1 the converse part is not necessarily true as given in the next upcoming Examples.

Example 3.1. Let $X = \{2, 4, 6\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{2\}, \{4\}, \{2, 4\}, X\}$.

If $\mathcal{G} = \{\{4\}, \{4, 6\}, X\}$.

1. $\{6\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set but not open.
2. $\{4\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set but not $\mathcal{G}_{t\#}$ -set.

Remark 3.3. These correlations are displayed in the representation.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \text{open} & \\
 & \downarrow & \\
 \mathcal{G}_{\alpha}\text{-open} & \longrightarrow & \mathcal{G}_p\text{-open} \\
 & \downarrow & \downarrow \\
 \mathcal{G}_s\text{-open} & \longrightarrow & \mathcal{G}_b\text{-open} \\
 & & \downarrow \\
 & & \mathcal{G}_{\beta}\text{-open}
 \end{array}$$

Proposition 3.1. If R and S are $\mathcal{G}_{t\#}$ -sets, then $R \cap S$ is $\mathcal{G}_{t\#}$ -set.

Proof.

Let R and S be $\mathcal{G}_{t\#}$ -sets. $I(R \cap S) \subseteq I(R \cap S) \subseteq \psi(I(R \cap S)) = \psi(I(R) \cap I(S)) \subseteq \psi(I(R)) \cap \psi(I(S)) = I(R) \cap I(S)$ (by guess) $= I(R \cap S)$.

Thus $I(R \cap S) = \psi(I(R \cap S))$ and hence $R \cap S$ is $\mathcal{G}_{t\#}$ -set. □

Theorem 3.1. The subsequent properties are equivalent for a subsets H of a grill topological space

1. B is open,
2. B is $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open & $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set.

Proof.

(1) implies (2): (1) of Remark 3.1 and (2) of Remark 3.3 come after each other.

(2) implies (1): Shown B is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set. So $B = R \cap S$ where R is open and $I(S) = \psi(I(S))$. Then $B \subseteq R = I(R)$. Also B is $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open implies $B \subseteq \psi(I(B)) \subseteq \psi(I(S)) = I(S)$ by guess. Thus $B \subseteq I(R) \cap I(S) = I(R \cap S) = I(R)$ and hence B is open. □

Remark 3.4. For a GLTS, the notions of $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -sets and of $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open sets are autonomous.

Example 3.2. In Example 3.1,

1. $\{4, 6\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open set but not $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set.
2. $\{6\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set but not $\mathcal{G}_s$ -open.

Remark 3.5. For a grill topological space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$,

1. if L is open $\implies L$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set.

2. if L is $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set $\implies L$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set.

Remark 3.6. The converse in the every part of Remark 3.5 is as noted in the next two examples, need not be accurate.

Example 3.3. In Example 3.1,

1. $\{6\}$ is not open but $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set.
2. $\{4\}$ is not $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set but $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set.

Proposition 3.2. If R and S are $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -sets of a space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$, then $R \cap S$ is $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set.

Proof.

Let R and S be $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -sets. $I(R \cap S) \subseteq I(R \cap S) \subseteq I(\psi(R \cap S)) \subseteq \psi(I(\psi(R \cap S))) \subseteq \psi(I(\psi(R))) \cap \psi(I(\psi(S))) = I(R) \cap I(S)$ (by guess) $= I(R \cap S)$.

Then $I(R \cap S) = \psi(I(\psi(R \cap S)))$ and subsequently, $R \cap S$ is $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set. □

Remark 3.7. The notions of $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open sets and $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -sets is a grill topological spaces are independent.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$ and $\tau = \{\phi, \{8\}, \{2, 6\}, \{2, 6, 8\}, X\}$.

If $\mathcal{G} = \{\{6\}, \{6, 8\}, X\}$.

1. $\{6, 8\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open set but not $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set.
2. $\{6\}$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set but not $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open.

Theorem 3.2. The following properties are equivalent for a subset H of a space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$.

1. T is open,
2. T is $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open and a $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set.

Proof.

(1) implies (2): (1) of Remark 3.5 and (2) of Remark 3.3 come after each other.

(2) implies (1) : Given T is a $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\alpha}^\#$ -set. So $T = R \cap S$ where R is open and S is $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set. Then $T \subseteq R = I(R)$. Also H is $\mathcal{G}_\beta$ -open implies $T \subseteq \psi(I(\psi(T))) \subseteq \psi(I(\psi(S))) = I(S)$ since S is $\mathcal{G}_{t\alpha}^\#$ -set.

Thus $T \subseteq I(R) \cap I(S) = I(R \cap S) = I(T)$ and thus T is open. □

Remark 3.8. The subsequent relations are true for a subset H of a space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$.

1. T is open $\implies T$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}}^\#$ -set.
2. T is $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set T with $I(\psi(T)) = \psi(I(T)) \implies T$ is $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}\#}$ -set.

Proof.

Proof follows straight, since the Definition of $\mathcal{G}_{S\mathcal{R}}$ -set. □

Remark 3.9. As mentioned in the next example, the converse of Remark 3.8(1) is not true.

Example 3.5. In Example 3.1, the set $\{4, 6\}$ is not open but $\mathcal{G}_{SR}$ -set.

Proposition 3.3. In a space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$, each $\mathcal{G}_{SR}$ -set is a $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}}$ -set.

Proof.

Proof follows from the note on that $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set T with $I(\psi(T)) = \psi(I(T))$ is $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set, which is a $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{R}}$ -set by of Definition 2.2. $\square$

Theorem 3.3. In a subset T of a space $(X, \mathcal{G}, I)$, the following properties are equivalent:

1. T is open;
2. T is $\mathcal{G}_b$ -open and $\mathcal{G}_{SR}$ -set.

Proof.

(1) implies (2): (1) of Remark 3.8 and (2) of Remark 3.3 come after each other.

(2) implies (1): Given T is $\mathcal{G}_{SR}$ -set. So $T = R \cap S$ where R is open and S is $\mathcal{G}_t$ -set with $I(\psi(S)) = \psi(I(S))$. Then $T \subseteq R = I(R)$. Also T is $\mathcal{G}_b$ -open implies $T \subseteq I(\psi(T)) \cup \psi(I(T)) \subseteq I(\psi(S)) \cup \psi(I(S)) = I(S)$ by guess. Thus $T \subseteq I(R) \cap I(S) = I(R \cap S) = I(T)$ and hence T is open. $\square$

Acknowledgement

The author is gracious to the referee for his or her enlightening comments and ideas.

References

- [1] A. Al-Omari and T. Noiri, *Decomposition of continuity via grilles*, Jordan J. Math. Stat., 4(1)(2011), 33-46.
- [2] G. Choquet, *Sur les notions de filter et grille*, Comptes Rendus Acad. Sci. Pairs., 224(1947), 171-173.
- [3] E. Hatir and S. Jafari, *On some new classes of sets and a new decomposition of continuity via grills*, J. Ads. Math. Studies, 3(1)(2010), 33-40.
- [4] N. Levine, *A decomposition of continuity in topological spaces*, Amer Math. Monthly., 68(1961), 36-41.
- [5] M. O. Mustafa and R. B. Esmael, *Separation axioms with grill-topological open set*, J. Phys. Conf. Ser., 1879(2)(2021), 022107.
- [6] M. O. Mustafa and R. B. Esmael, *Some properties in grill-topological open and closed sets*, J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 1897(1)(2021), 012038.
- [7] O. Nethaji, R. Asokan and I. Rajasekaran, *Novel concept of ideal nanotopological spaces*, Asia Mathematika, 3(3)(2019), 84-88.
- [8] I. Rajasekaran, O. Nethaji, S. Jackson and N. Sekar, *Some improvised sets in grill topological spaces*, Annals of Communications in Mathematics, 5(3)(2022), 207-211
- [9] I. Rajasekaran, *On $*b$ -open sets and $*b$ -sets in nano topological spaces*, Asia Mathematika, 5(3)(2021), 5-15.
- [10] V. Renukadevi, *Relation between ideals and grills*, J. Adv. Res. Pure Math. 2(4)(2010), 9-14.
- [11] B. Roy and M. N. Mukherjee, *On a typical topology induced by a grill*, Soochow J. Math., 33(2007), 771-786.
- [12] D. Saravanakumar and N. Kalaivani, *On grill S_p -open set in grill topological spaces*, J. New Theory, 23(2018), 85-92.
- [13] N. Sekar, R. Asokan and I. Rajasekaran, *On S_p^* -open sets in ideal nano topological spaces*, Asia Mathematika, 6(2)(2022), 39-47.
- [14] W. J. Thron, *Proximity structure and grills*, Math. Ann., 206(1973), 35-62.